

REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN ACADEMY OF LAW ENFORCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article details the activities of prosecutors, improving the skills of prosecutors, the Academy of Law Enforcement of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the structure, objectives and functions of the Academy, the leadership of the Academy, and networks.

Since the early days of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there has been a special emphasis on improving the quality of prosecutors' offices, along with improving the activities of prosecutors.

The era itself prohibited the need to further improve the system of preparing, rehabilitating, and improving the standards of prosecutors' offices, as well as the new priorities of socio-economic development in the country, the responsibilities of upholding the rule of law and strengthening the law.

In the intervening period, a comprehensive analysis of the state of law enforcement, taking measures to address the causes and conditions of violations in a timely manner, ensuring the protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens, and teaching the necessary knowledge and skills to support business entities has been developed.

At the same time, the fact that absolutely new approaches to the work of prosecutors' bodies have been identified, their role in the reforms and changes being implemented has required the formation of appropriate personnel that can effectively carry out the tasks entrusted to them.

In accordance with the tasks set out in the Action Strategy for the five pillars of National Development during 2017-2021, as well as to create an innovative system for preparing, rehabilitating and improving the standards of prosecutors, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan stated: "Improving the system of preparing, rehabilitating and improving the standards of prosecutors 2Pf-5438 of May 8, 2018 was adopted. According to the decree,

higher education courses of the Office of the Attorney-General of Uzbekistan were reorganized as the Academy of Public Prosecutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In accordance with the PF-257 Order of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on November 28, 2022, "On the implementation of a qualitatively new system for the preparation of qualified personnel in the field of criminal investigation,"³ the Academy of Public Prosecutions established the Academy of Law Enforcement of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Academy of Law Enforcement of the Republic of Uzbekistan as an educational and research institution:

- training, retraining and professional development of qualified personnel in the field of criminal investigation;
- preparation of personnel on the basis of audit and payment contracts, with a bachelor's degree, a master's degree and a diploma in the country's template;
- professional retraining of candidates for positions in the prosecutor's office in the form of primary specialization;
- professional retraining of reserved personnel for positions of directing in the prosecutor's office;
- professional development of employees of state bodies and other organizations on issues of law enforcement, cooperation in the fight against crime and corruption on the basis of short-term programs;
- training of highly qualified scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel in accordance with the legislation;
- all types of educational, methodological, research, information and information activities involving national, foreign and international grants;
- to send teachers, staff and students to internships in state authorities, government and economic management bodies, public organizations, as well as in higher education and research institutions, including foreign countries;
- performs publishing activities.

Programs for the training, retraining and professional development of personnel at the Academy are carried out in accordance with the established procedure.

The Academy introduced a continuous training system aimed at preparing personnel in the field of crime investigation on the basis of a single approach, ensuring their incompatibility with practice.

Goals and tasks

The main objective of the Academy is to take the practice of preparing and rehabilitating qualified personnel in the field of criminal investigation in New Uzbekistan to a qualitative phase, to expand international standards and modern information technology in this direction and to meet the needs of law enforcement agencies for high-level personnel, as well as to train prosecutors and other personnel, to organize an effective system of retraining and advanced training and conduct fundamental and scientific research.

Main functions and directions of activity:

- establishment of a unified system of training, retraining and professional development of employees, ensuring the development and strengthening of the knowledge and skills of employees of the prosecutor's office, including systematic analysis and critical thinking, the

development and improvement of personal and employment qualities, the justice and responsibility for the unconditional observance of laws, the rights and freedoms of citizens;

- wide introduction of modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies, distance learning, interactive and problematic methods of teaching and training;
- providing scientific and methodological support for the activities of prosecutors, conducting fundamental, practical and innovative research, upholding the rule of law, strengthening legality, protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens and business entities, the interests of society and the state protected by law, systematically conducting research programs and projects on actual problems of law enforcement profiling implementation, including with the involvement of national, foreign and international grants;
- development of scientific-based conclusions and recommendations on improving legislation and the formation of unified law enforcement practices;
- training of specialists in bachelor's and master's degrees, based on the practical characteristics of teaching and incompatibility with the professional activities of the prosecutor's office;
- professional development of employees of state bodies and other organizations on issues of interaction in the field of law enforcement, the fight against crime and corruption;
- development of recommendations on psychological support of the activities of prosecutors, professional and psychological selection of candidates for admission to the service, studying and improving the moral and psychological environment of the prosecutor's office;
- conducting scientific research in cooperation, exchanging information of regulatory, methodological and analytical nature, attracting foreign specialists to the learning process, conducting international cooperation in the field of systematic organization of internships of teachers, academics and listeners;
- exchange of experience in improving the quality of the educational process, deepening effective interdepartmental cooperation with institutions of foreign countries, including education and research that prepares, rehabilitate and improves legal standards, in order to unite efforts;
- attract highly qualified specialists in the educational process and scientific and methodical work, conduct contractual consultations, as well as establish cooperation and contracts with foreign educational, research institutions in the field of training, retraining and advanced training of management personnel;
- targeted training of specialists in the field of crime investigation, introducing an effective system for the development of high spiritual, psychological, analytical and professional qualities in students harmonized with the culture of unconditional observance of human rights and freedoms;
- apply interfaith teaching methods to the teaching process aimed at developing the ability to operate independently in criminal cases based on effective determination of the methods and tactics of investigating crimes;
- preparation of highly qualified scientific and pedagogical personnel, systematic implementation of comprehensive scientific research on the most pressing issues of law enforcement activities;

- analyze and diagnostics of the causes and conditions of crimes, including the study of investigative documents and criminal cases, as well as methodological and consultative provision of prevention of offenses and the fight against crime;
- conducting joint scientific research in the field of forensics, continuous international cooperation in the exchange of advanced pedagogical experience, attracting qualified specialists from leading higher education and research organizations in foreign countries to the educational process.

Head of the Academy of Law Enforcement:

- ✓ Samadov Salom Ismatovich

Head of the Academy of Law Enforcement, etc.

- ✓ Kolenko Yevgeniy Vyacheslavovich

First Deputy Head of Academy

- ✓ Turaxanov Durbek Lermonovich

Deputy Head of Academy

- ✓ Nigmatjanov Uygun Uchkunovich

Deputy Head of Academy

- ✓ Mamasiddiqov Bahrijon Musajonovich

Deputy Head of Academy

Chairs

- Department of Criminal Law and Criminology
- Department of Preliminary Investigation and Investigation
- Department of Forensics and Forensics
- Department of Prosecutor's Activities and Prosecutor's Supervision
- Department of Investigation and Cyber Law
- Department of Prosecutor's Office and Execution in Courts
- Department of State legal sciences
- Department of Professional Psychology and Management Activities
- Department of International Law and Human Rights Protection
- Department of Social and Humanities
- Department of Language Teaching
- Department of military and physical training
- Department of Economic Crime and Legalization of Criminal Revenues

Centers

- Center for Scientific and Practical Research on problems of law enforcement activities
- Center for coordination of scientific innovation research and training of researchers
- Anti-Corruption Research Center · Office-Registrar Center
- Scientific and Methodological Center for Digital Forensics Sections
- Department of organizational control and effectiveness assessment
- Personal Security Division · Department of Public Relations
- Legal Department
- First and second sections

- Department of Accounting and Planning and Finance
- Department of Business Administration
- Department of information and communication technologies and information security
- Department of youth work, spirituality and enlightenment
- Project Management Department
- Department of International Cooperation
- Editorial publishing department
- Department of electronic education

HR Department Faculties

- Bachelor's degree faculties
- Master's degree faculties
- Faculty of Retraining and Training Management
- Educational and methodical management

References:

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